

Supracrestal Tissue Attachment : A Modern Take on the Classic Biologic Width Concept

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Abstract

The concept of biologic width, now redefined as supracrestal tissue attachment (STA), plays a pivotal role in maintaining periodontal health and ensuring the longevity of restorative treatments. The term STA emerged from the 2017 World Workshop on the Classification of Periodontal and Peri-implant Diseases and Conditions, superseding the traditional terminology. STA encompasses the junctional epithelium and supracrestal connective tissue, forming a critical barrier that protects the underlying alveolar bone from microbial invasion and trauma. The historical evolution of biologic width, originating with the foundational work of Cohen and Gargiulo, underscores its importance in restorative dentistry, particularly in the placement of subgingival margins. Disruption or violation of this dimension can lead to inflammation, attachment loss, and alveolar bone resorption, necessitating precise diagnostic and treatment strategies. Clinical evaluation methods, including bone sounding and radiographic techniques, are essential for assessing STA and preventing restorative margins from encroaching upon this delicate space. Future research aims to enhance our understanding of STA dynamics around implants and natural teeth, contributing to improved periodontal and restorative outcomes.

Key Words : Supracrestal Tissue Attachment, Biologic Width, Periodontal Health, Restorative Dentistry, Gingival Margins

Introduction

Supracrestal tissue attachment (STA)¹ is a relatively new term that was introduced in 2017 following the World Workshop on the Classification of Periodontal and Peri-implant Diseases and Conditions, co-sponsored by the American Academy of Periodontology (AAP) and the European Federation of Periodontology (EFP), which included expert participants from all over the world. It has replaced the term biological width, and refers to the junctional epithelium and supracrestal connective tissue.

Biological width: what is it? The human body is susceptible to invasion by a wide range of germs, diseases, and foreign particles. Ectodermal tissue helps guard against disease-causing organisms. The biological width (BW) that is derived from the ectoderm refers to the innate protective barrier that forms around the alveolus, protecting it from infections and diseases.²

Over the years, different authors have defined the BW differently,

Authors	Year	Definition
Ingber J et al. & Amiri-Jezeh M et al.	1977 & 2006	"The junctional epithelium and supracrestal connective tissue attachment surrounding every tooth."
Nevin et al.	1984	"The sum of the combined supracrestal fibers, the junctional epithelium, and the sulcus."
Khuler N et al. & Nugala B et al. (most accepted)	2009 & 2012	"The dimension of the soft tissue, which is attached to the portion of the tooth coronal to the crest of the alveolar bone."
World Workshop on the Classification of Periodontal and Peri-Implant Disease and Conditions	2018	"Commonly used clinical term to describe the apico-coronal variable dimensions of the supracrestal attached tissues."

Table 1: Definitions of biologic width by different authors.3,4,5,6,7,8

History of Biological Width

Cohen coined the term "biological width" in 1962 to refer to the biological attachment of the soft tissues to the tooth's root. This attachment includes both connective tissue and junctional epithelium, and it is the distance between the alveolar bone crest and the base of the gingival sulcus.⁹

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This term was coined following the work by Gargiulo et al in 1961, in which the width is referred to as the dentogingival junction.¹⁰ The dentogingival junction consists of two parts: connective tissue attachment and epithelial attachment.

In 2017, the World Workshop on the Classification of Periodontal and Peri-implant Diseases and Conditions changed the word 'biological width' to 'supracrestal tissue attachment' (STA), which refers to the junctional epithelium and supracrestal connective tissue. The workshop was co-sponsored by the American Academy of Periodontology (AAP) and the European Federation of Periodontology (EFP), with expert attendees from all around the world.¹

Anatomy of Biological Width

Figure 1. Diagram illustrating the dimensions based on the research of Gargiulo et al.¹⁰

The term "biological width" originates from Gargiulo et al.'s 1961 study,¹⁰ which analyzed the dentogingival complex in 287 human cadaver teeth. The research revealed proportional relationships between the alveolar crest, connective tissue attachment, epithelial attachment, and sulcus depth. The average measurements were 0.69 mm for sulcus depth, 0.97 mm for epithelial attachment, and 1.07 mm for connective tissue attachment, totaling 2.04 mm for biological width. However, biological width varies individually, with Vacek et al. (1994)¹¹ reporting a range of 0.75 mm to 4 mm.

Importance or Significance of STA

STA is a type of human tissue barrier that protects against infection and foreign materials by responding dynamically to keep a consistent distance.⁵ If this distance is crossed, a cellular reaction will occur to restore the proper distance between the restoration's edge and the bone crest.

The supracrestal tissue attachment (STA) is crucial in restorative dentistry, especially for subgingival margins. Dentists must avoid disrupting the junctional epithelium or connective tissue during preparation and impression recording. Since distinguishing the junctional and sulcular epithelium is challenging, subgingival margins should extend only 0.5-1.0 mm below the gingival level.⁵

In natural dentition, tooth shape influences gingival morphology. Tooth forms include triangular, ovoid, square, long narrow, and short wide. Triangular teeth have incisal proximal contacts and require more tissue height, increasing the risk of "black hole disease." In contrast, square teeth have longer proximal contacts and less papillary tissue, reducing this risk.¹²

Dimensions of Periodontium

Maynard and Wilson¹³ classified the periodontium into three dimensions: superficial physiologic gingiva, which surrounds the teeth in its free and attached state. The crevicular dimension refers to the distance between the junctional epithelium and the gingival edge. Subcrevicular physiology refers to the biological width of the connective tissue connection and junctional epithelium.

Supracrestal Tissue Violation

Inflammation, pocket formation, osseous resorption, irreversible loss of periodontal attachment, and in rare cases, root resorption can result from supracrestal tissue violation. Patients with a thin gingival tissue biotype (gingival thickness <1.5 mm) are more likely to have recession, while those with a thick gingival biotype (gingival thickness >2 mm) are more likely to experience inflammation and periodontal pocketing.

STA Clinical Evaluation

Using a periodontal probe, BW is measured in clinic settings. It is determined that there is a violation of BW when the distance is smaller than 2 mm at one or more sites. For accurate gauging, measurements should be made on multiple teeth with healthy gingiva to reduce the possibility of site and individual variances.^{7,14}

Evaluation of STA Violation

Clinical Method¹⁵

It is a strong sign that the margin extends into the attachment and that a biologic width violation has taken place if the patient feels discomfort in their tissue while the restoration margin levels are being measured with a periodontal probe.

The signs of biologic width violation are:

- Chronic progressive gingival inflammation around the restoration.
- Bleeding on probing.
- Localized gingival hyperplasia with minimal bone loss.
- Gingival recession.
- Pocket formation.
- Clinical attachment loss.
- Alveolar bone loss.
- Gingival hyperplasia (most frequently found in altered passive eruption and subgingivally placed restoration margins).

Bone Sounding/Transgingival Probing¹⁶

Biologic width is measured by probing to the bone level under local anesthesia ("sounding to bone") and subtracting the sulcus depth from the total measurement. A distance of less than 2 mm at any site indicates a biologic width violation.

Figure 2: Signs of biologic width violation - inflammation and bone loss.¹⁵

Radiographic evaluation¹⁷

- Radiographs can detect interproximal biologic width violations but are unreliable for mesiofacial and distofacial line angles due to tooth overlap.
- The parallel profile technique offers precise measurements of the dentogingival unit's length and thickness.

Categories/profiles of Biologic Width

Kois^{18,19} proposed three categories of biologic width based on the total dimension of attachment and the sulcus depth following bone sounding measurements:

- Normal crest.
- Low crest.
- High crest.

	Normal Crest	High crest	Low crest
Mid-facial measurement	3 mm	<3 mm	>3 mm
Proximal measurement	3 – 4.5 mm	<3 mm	>4.5 mm

Fig 3 : Transgingival Probing/Bonesounding¹⁶

Normal Crest Patient (85%)²⁰

Gingival tissue remains stable long-term. A crown margin should be placed at least 2.5 mm from the alveolar bone. A 0.5 mm subgingival crown margin is well-tolerated and stable in these patients.

High crest patient (2%)²⁰

Figure 4: Categories of biologic width.¹⁸

Typically found near edentulous areas, where placing an intracrevicular margin is not possible due to proximity to the alveolar bone, leading to biologic width impingement and chronic inflammation.

Low Crest Patient (13%)²⁰

These patients are more prone to recession from intracrevicular crown margins, as retraction cord placement often injures the attachment apparatus. Healing may return tissue to a normal crest position, causing recession. Low crest patients vary in response; those with a shallow sulcus and stable attachment are less prone to recession, while those with a deeper sulcus and narrower attachment are more susceptible to it.

Margin Placement

Ingber et al. (1977)²¹ Ingber et al. (1977) proposed that a minimum of 3 mm should be maintained between the restorative margin and the alveolar crest to ensure proper healing and restoration of the tooth.

Maynard and Wilson (1979)²² Maynard and Wilson (1979) classified the periodontium into three functional zones that influence restorative decisions:

- Superficial physiologic: The free and attached gingiva around the tooth.
- Crevicular physiologic: The gingival area extending from the gingival margin to the junctional epithelium.
- Subcrevicular physiologic: Equivalent to the biologic width (as described by Gargiulo et al., 1961), including the junctional epithelium and connective tissue attachment.

Nevins and Skurow (1984)²³ Nevins and Skurow (1984) highlighted the need to protect the junctional epithelium and connective tissue when preparing and recording impressions for subgingival margins. They advised limiting the subgingival margin extension to 0.5-1.0 mm, as it is difficult for clinicians to precisely distinguish where the sulcular epithelium ends and the junctional

epithelium begins. A minimum distance of 3.0 mm from the alveolar crest to the crown margin is essential.

Margin placement - Rules²⁴

1. If the sulcus probes 1.5 mm or less, the restorative margin could be placed 0.5 mm below the gingival tissue crest.
2. If the sulcus probes >1.5 mm, the restorative margin can be placed in half the depth of the sulcus.
3. If the sulcus is >2 mm, gingivectomy could be performed to lengthen the tooth, and create a 1.5 mm sulcus.

Then the patient can be treated as per rule¹.

Supragingival margin²⁵

- Supragingival margins have minimal impact on the periodontium.
- Traditionally used in non-esthetic areas due to the stark contrast in color and opacity between restorative materials and the tooth.
- With the development of translucent restorative materials, adhesive dentistry, and resin cements, placing supragingival margins in esthetic areas has become feasible.

Figure 5 : Supra Gingival Margin²⁵

Advantages

1. Tooth preparation and margin finishing are simpler.
2. Impressions can be easily removed past the finish line without tearing or distortion, making supragingival margins ideal for duplication.
3. Supragingival margins cause the least irritation to the periodontal tissue.

Equigingival Margin²⁰

Equigingival margins were once avoided due to concerns about plaque accumulation, gingival inflammation, and unsightly margins from minor recession. However, these concerns are no longer valid, as modern restorations can blend esthetically with the tooth and be easily finished for a smooth, polished gingival margin.

Subgingival Margin²⁶

- Restoration margins are often placed below the gingival crest to address caries, tooth deficiencies, or mask the tooth/restoration interface.
- If the margin is too deep, it can irritate the gingival attachment, causing chronic inflammation and cleaning difficulties.
- The body attempts to create space between the alveolar

bone and margin for tissue reattachment, leading to gingival recession and bone loss.

- This is more common in areas with thin alveolar bone.
- Thin, scalloped gingiva is more prone to recession than flat, fibrous tissue.
- With deep margin placement, bone levels often remain unchanged, but gingival inflammation persists around the restoration.

When placing the margin subgingivally, consider the following factors

- Correct crown contour in the gingival third.
- Proper polishing.
- The margins are rounded.
- A sufficient zone of connected gingiva.
- There is no infringement of biological width.

Biological Width Around Implants

- Two-piece implants have a wider biological width than single-piece implants and natural teeth.
- The existence and location of a microgap alter the soft tissue and bone levels.
- Connective tissue around implants is more stable than the epithelial dimension.²⁷
- Biological width is a physiological reaction in the oral cavity that does not depend on loading quantity or quality.²⁸
- One-piece implants and natural teeth have more stable connective tissue dimensions. However, the junctional epithelium is constantly threatened by microbial growth and pathogenic microbial products.
- The biological width around the implant undergoes structural and histologic alterations similar to those seen around the tooth, regardless of tissue type.²⁹

Diagnostics And Planning

- Localized gingival recession or bone loss with good hygiene may indicate an overextended restoration impinging on STA.
- STA should be considered during restorative planning to prevent damage.
- Maintain 3 mm between the restoration margin and alveolar bone to avoid STA impingement (1 mm connective tissue, 1 mm junctional epithelium, 1 mm sulcus).^{11,30}
- Individual STA variations may require more than 3 mm.
- Subgingival margins should extend only 0.5–1.0 mm to avoid damaging the junctional epithelium.
- Crown margins impinging on STA cause localized inflammation, distinguishable from gingivitis, often unrelated to plaque.
- Correction may involve improving hygiene, crown lengthening, or crown replacement.

Correction of Violation of STA

- **Risk Factors** : Restorations near the alveolar crest (cracks or caries) risk encroaching on biological width.
- **Aesthetic Considerations** : Subgingival placement of restoration margins may violate biological width.

- **Variation** : Biological width differs between individuals and sites within the same patient.
- **Assessment** : Each site must be evaluated to avoid anatomical disruption.
- **Goal** : Respect anatomical integrity during restorative procedures.

Figure 7 : A clinical photograph to demonstrate gingival inflammation caused by the crowns on UR1 and UR2 impinging on the biological width.¹

Surgical Crown Lengthening

Crown lengthening treatment is tailored to each patient, taking into account the connection between the crown and root of the alveolar bones.

Surgical crown lengthening	Orthodontic procedures
Gingivectomy; External bevel or internal bevel gingivectomy	Can be slow, rapid, forced tooth eruption with or without fibrotomy, supracrestal fibrotomy, and root planing (OEFRP)
Apical repositioned flap (ARF) surgery; with or without osseous reduction	

Table 2 : Methods of biological width correction.³²

Indications	Contraindications	Complications
Deficient clinical crown for retention because of deep and extensively large caries lesions, cemental/subgingival/root caries, or any type of tooth fracture, root perforation, or resorption within the cervical 1/3rd of the root in the teeth with suitable periodontal attachments	Deep carious or fractured tooth requiring an excessive amount of bone removal	Poor esthetics due to the presence of black triangles
Short or insufficient clinical crowns	Unjustified compromise of esthetics and/or of adjacent alveolar bone support	Root hypersensitivity
Excessive, unequal, and/or unesthetic gingival levels with respect to esthetics	Teeth that cannot be restored	Root resorption
Tooth with an imprudent amount of incisal or occlusal wear	Tooth depicting increased risk of furcation involvement	Transient tooth mobility
Teeth exhibiting weak interocclusal space for proper restorative procedures because of supraeruption		
Teeth exhibiting weak interocclusal space for proper restorative procedures because of supraeruption		
Tooth in need of hemisection or root resection		

Table 3 : Indications, contraindications, and complications of surgical crown lengthening.^{7,33}

Methods for Surgical Crown Lengthening

Techniques for Correcting Biological Width Violation

1. External Bevel Gingivectomy³⁴

- Reduces excessive pocket depth and exposes coronal tooth structure.
- Suitable when attached gingiva is abundant, with no bone involvement.

2. Internal Bevel Gingivectomy⁶

- Reduces deep pockets and exposes coronal tooth structure.

- Indicated even in the absence of sufficient attached gingiva.
- Internally beveled flap exposes alveolar bone, addressing osseous irregularities if necessary.

3. Apical Repositioned Flap (ARF) Surgery³⁵

- Ideal for crown lengthening across multiple teeth in a quadrant.
- Not recommended for single-tooth procedures, especially in esthetic zones.

4. ARF Without Osseous Reduction³⁵

- Suitable when biological width exceeds 3 mm with adequate attached gingiva.

5. ARF With Osseous Reduction³⁵

- Indicated for biological width <3 mm and insufficient attached gingiva.
- Osteotomy and osteoplasty expose sufficient tooth structure, ensuring proper gingival contour.
- At least 4 mm of sound tooth structure must be exposed to account for coronal soft tissue regrowth, leaving 1-2 mm of supragingival tooth structure.

Note : Although Gargiulo et al.¹⁰ established a supracrestal tissue attachment of 2 mm, clinical measurement during crown margin preparation remains challenging.

Figure 9:37 Series of clinical photographs to demonstrate the crown lengthening procedure (APF with osseous reduction) on a patient with tooth surface loss. (a) Probe markings. (b) UR1 and UL1 incisions. (c) Flap raised. (d) Stent in situ before bone removal. (e) Stent in situ following bone removal demonstrating 3 mm of osseous reduction. (f) Simple interrupted intra-papillary sutures.

Implants

1. STA Differences in Implants

- Implants exhibit a supracrestal tissue attachment (STA), but this is primarily based on animal studies (e.g., dogs), as proposed by Misch et al.³⁶
- Unlike natural teeth, implants integrate through osseointegration, resulting in ankylosis and minimal or no connective tissue fiber attachment.

2. Connective Tissue Characteristics¹

- In implants, connective tissue comprises primarily parallel and circular fiber groups, lacking the perpendicular fiber attachment seen in natural teeth.
- The implant is sealed by epithelial hemi-desmosomes, contributing to its stability.

3. Structural Differences¹

- Absence of periodontal ligament (PDL) reduces the implant's capacity to absorb and distribute occlusal forces.
- The tissue surrounding implants is hypovascular and hypocellular, with increased collagen content compared to the natural tooth environment.

4. Biological Width and Variation

- Misch et al.³⁸ measured an average biological width of 3.08 mm around implants.
- Herman et al.³⁹ noted that biological width may vary depending on implant type (e.g., one-piece vs. two-piece, submerged vs. non-submerged).

5. Clinical Implications¹

- Reduced vascularity and lack of connective tissue attachment contribute to thicker STA around implants.
- This structural difference can result in deeper clinical probing depths and less predictable bleeding on probing, making peri-implant health assessments more challenging.

Figure 10 : Schematic demonstrating differences between supracrestal tissue attachment around teeth and implants.¹

Conclusion

The concept of biologic width, now recognized as supracrestal tissue attachment (STA), remains a cornerstone in periodontal and restorative dentistry, ensuring the health and longevity of both natural teeth and implants. STA serves as a critical protective barrier, safeguarding underlying alveolar bone from microbial invasion and mechanical trauma. Its dynamic nature demands

precise management to prevent clinical complications such as inflammation, gingival recession, and bone loss. As research continues to refine our understanding of STA, particularly around implants, clinicians must prioritize careful margin placement and thorough diagnostic assessments, moreover adhering to these principles will help preserve periodontal integrity and optimize long-term treatment outcomes.

References

1. Shah J, Webb L, McColl E, Daldry M, Bhagi S, Witton R. Supracrestal tissue attachment: an update. *Dent Update*. 2024;50(1):707-9.
2. Makigusa K: Histologic comparison of biologic width around teeth versus implant: the effect on bone preservation. *J Implant Reconstr Dent*. 2009, 12:20-4.
3. Ingber JS, Rose LF, Coslet JG: The "biologic width"--a concept in periodontics and restorative dentistry . *Alpha Omegan*. 1977,70:62-5.
4. Amiri-Jezeh M, Rateitschak E, Weiger R, Walter C: The impact of the margin of restorations on periodontal health--a review (Article in German). *Schweiz MonatsschrZahnmed*. 2006, 116:606-13.
5. Nevins M, Skurow HM: The intracrevicular restorative margin, the biologic width, and the maintenance of the gingival margin. *Int J Periodontics Restorative Dent*. 1984, 4:30-49.
6. Khuller N, Sharma N: Biologic width: evaluation and correction of its violation . *J Oral Heal Comm Dent*. 2009, 3:20-5. 10.5005/johcd-3-1-20
7. Nugala B, Kumar BS, Sahitya S, Krishna PM: Biologic width and its importance in periodontal and restorative dentistry. *J Conserv Dent*. 2012, 15:12-7. 10.4103/0972-0707.92599
8. Bhochhibhoya A, Shrestha R: Biologic width-a review . *J Nepal Prosthodont Soc*. 2020, 3:106-14. 10.3126/jnprossoc.v3i2.36387
9. Cohen DW. Washington DC, USA: Walter Reed Army Medical Center; 1962
10. Gargiulo AW, Wentz FM, Orban B Dimensions and relations of the dentogingival junction in humans. *J Periodontol*. 1961; 32:261-267 <https://doi.org/10.1902/jop.1961.32.3.261>
11. Vacek JS, Gher ME, Assad DA The dimensions of the human dentogingival junction. *Int J Periodontics Restorative Dent*. 1994; 14:154-165
12. Dhir S: The peri-implant esthetics: an unforgettable entity . *J Indian Soc Periodontol*. 2011, 15:98-103. 10.4103/0972-124X.84375
13. Maynard JG Jr, Wilson RD: Physiologic dimensions of the periodontium significant to the restorative dentist. *J Periodontol*. 1979, 50:170-4. 10.1902/jop.1979.50.4.170
14. Sharma A, Rahul G, Gupta B, Hafeez M: Biological width: no violation zone .*Eur J Gen Dent*. 2012, 1:137-41. 10.4103/2278-9626.105353
15. Jorgic-Srdjak K, Plancak D, Maricevic T, Dragoo MR, Bosnjak A. Periodontal and prosthetic aspect of biological width part I: Violation of biologic width. *Acta Stomatol Croat* 2000; 34:195-7.

16. Newmann MG, Takei H, Klokkevold PR. Carranza's Clinical Periodontology. 10th ed. Philadelphia: Saunders, Elsevier Publishing; 2006. p. 1050-69
17. Galgali SR, Gontiya G. Evaluation of an innovative radiographic technique — Parallel profile radiography — To determine the dimensions of dentogingival unit. *Indian J Dent Res* 2011;22:237-41
18. Kois J. Altering gingival levels: The restorative connection, Part 1: Biologic variables. *J Esthet Dent* 1994;6:3-9.
19. Kois JC. The restorative-periodontal interface: Biological parameters. *Periodontol* 2000 1996;11:29-38.
20. Aishwarya M, Sivaram G. Biologic width: Concept and violation. *SRM J Res Dent Sci* 2015;6:250-6
21. Ingber JS, Rose LF, Coslet JG. The “biologic width” — A concept in periodontics and restorative dentistry. *Alpha Omegan* 1977;70:62-5.
22. Maynard JG Jr, Wilson RD. Physiologic dimensions of the periodontium significant to the restorative dentist. *J Periodontol* 1979;50:170-4.
23. Nevins M, Skurow HM. The intracrevicular restorative margin, the biologic width, and the maintenance of the gingival margin. *Int J Periodontics Restorative Dent* 1984;4:30-49.
24. Orkin DA, Reddy J, Bradshaw D. The relationship of the position of crown margins to gingival health. *J Prosthet Dent* 1987;57:421-4.
25. Khuller N, Sharma N. Biologic width: Evaluation and correction of its violation. *J Oral Health Community Dent* 2009;3:20-5.
26. Nugala B, Kumar BS, Sahitya S, Krishna PM. Biologic width and its importance in periodontal and restorative dentistry. *J Conserv Dent* 2012;15:12-7.
27. Hermann JS, Schoolfield JD, Schenk RK, Buser D, Cochran DL: Influence of the size of the microgap on crestal bone changes around titanium implants. A histometric evaluation of unloaded non-submerged implants in the canine mandible. *J Periodontol.* 2001, 72:1372-83. 10.1902/jop.2001.72.10.1372.
28. Lindhe J, Berglundh T, Ericsson I, Liljenberg B, Marinello C: Experimental breakdown of peri-implant and periodontal tissues. A study in the beagle dog. *Clin Oral Implants Res.* 1992, 3:9-16.
29. Kawahara H, Kawahara D, Mimura Y, Takashima Y, Ong JL: Morphologic studies on the biologic seal of titanium dental implants. Report II. In vivo study on the defending mechanism of epithelial adhesions/attachment against invasive factors. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Implants.* 1998, 13:465-73
30. Nevins M, Skurow HM. The intracrevicular restorative margin, the biologic width, and the maintenance
31. Mishkin DJ, Gellin RG: Re: biologic width and crown lengthening,. *J Periodontol.* 1993, 64:920. of the gingival margin. *Int J Periodontics Restorative Dent.* 1984; 4:30-49
32. Schmidt JC, Sahrman P, Weiger R, Schmidlin PR, Walter C: Biologic width dimensions - a systematic review. *J Clin Periodontol.* 2013, 40:493-504. 10.1111/jcpe.12078
33. Jorgić-Srdjak K, Dragoo MR, Botnjak A, Plancak D, Filipovic I, Lazić D: Periodontal and prosthetic aspect of the biological width part II: reconstruction of anatomy and function. *Acta Stomatol Croat.* 2000, 33:441-4.
34. Smukler H, Chaibi M: Periodontal and dental considerations in clinical crown extension: a rational basis for treatment. *Int J Periodontics Restorative Dent.* 1997, 17:464-77
35. Mulla S A, Patil A, Mali S, et al. (July 18, 2023) Exploring the Biological Width in Dentistry: A Comprehensive Narrative Review. *Cureus* 15(7): e42080. DOI 10.7759/cureus.42080
36. Misch CE, Perel ML, Wang HL Implant success, survival, and failure: the International Congress of Oral Implantologists (ICOI) Pisa Consensus Conference. *Implant Dent.* 2008; 17:5-15
37. Berglundh T, Lindhe J. Dimension of the periimplant mucosa. Biological width revisited. *J Clin Periodontol.* 1996; 23:971-973
38. Hermann JS, Buser D, Schenk RK Biologic width around titanium implants. A physiologically formed and stable dimension over time. *Clin Oral Implants Res.* 2000; 11:1-11
39. Jepsen S, Caton JG, Albandar JM Periodontal manifestations of systemic diseases and developmental and acquired conditions: Consensus report of workgroup 3 of the 2017 World Workshop on the Classification of Periodontal and Peri-Implant Diseases and Conditions. *J Clin Periodontol.* 2018; 45:S219-S229